

THE IMPACT OF PHOSPHOROUS FERTILIZERS ON SOIL ECOLOGY

A. Jumamuratov¹, N. Bazarbaeva²

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajniyaz^{1,2}

Professor of the Department of Physics Teaching Methods¹, Master's student of the Department
of Physics Teaching Methods²

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Abstract. *This study focuses on determining the elemental composition of the topsoil and phosphorous fertilizers using the neutron activation analysis method and examining the impact of excessive accumulation of microelements in the soil on soil ecology.*

Keywords: *phosphorous fertilizers, ecology, neutron-activation analysis, element, cotton, soil, productivity, agricultural lands, comparison.*

Introduction

Soil, as the productive upper layer of the Earth, is considered one of the key components of the biosphere [1.2.5-7]. It plays a fundamental role in sustaining life. Essential nutrients and raw materials for industries are extracted from soil, including crops like cotton, rice, melons, and fruits. Before planting crops, it is necessary to determine the elemental composition of the soil in the area. This helps identify the chemical elements present, their quantities, and which plants would yield the best results when grown there.

Determining the levels of chemical elements affecting soil productivity allows for understanding the impact of various technical measures and taking preventive actions. The average chemical composition of the soil's upper layer often differs from the average chemical composition of the Earth's crust. The general soil composition contains more than 40 chemical elements, which describe the soil's structure. Many of these are trace elements, present in concentrations of less than 0.05% [2]. Phosphorous fertilizers are considered highly effective in improving soil structure and increasing productivity. When used according to specified norms, these fertilizers do not cause adverse effects. However, when their concentration in the soil increases, the accumulation of heavy elements in the fertilizers reduces the plant's ability to absorb nutrients. Therefore, applying phosphorous fertilizers based on the soil's elemental map is crucial for enhancing productivity.

The primary aim of this study is to analyze soil samples from agricultural lands in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and to study the elemental composition of phosphorous fertilizers. The research focuses on the impact of prolonged overuse of these fertilizers, which leads to the accumulation of heavy microelements in agricultural soils, and its subsequent effect on soil ecology.

Research Methods and Equipment

We study the elemental composition of soil and phosphate waste using the neutron activation analysis method. Soil samples are collected from agricultural fields using the composite sampling method [3]. Each sample, weighing 100 mg, is packaged together with an SP-1 [4] type standard sample and placed in the vertical channel of a reactor. The samples are irradiated with

neutron flux for 10–15 minutes to identify short-lived elements and up to 1 hour to detect long-lived elements.

For this, multielement neutron activation analysis is performed using a VVP-CM type nuclear reactor, with neutron sources such as (^{252}Cf , Po+Be) and **Po+Be** (Polonium-Beryllium). Irradiated samples are analyzed with a high-resolution gamma spectrometer of Ge(Li), with energy ranging from 1.5 to 3.5 keV.

The reliability of microelement determination in soil composition is high ($P > 0.997$). Elements such as Au (gold), U (uranium), Hg (mercury), Th (thorium), La (lanthanum), and Sb (antimony) are identified based on their intensities $I_{\pi} \leq 3\sqrt{I_{\phi}}$. Special attention is required for the analysis of Au and Hg due to their higher concentrations, which also necessitate the use of radiochemical methods.

Results and Discussion

Currently, the use of phosphorus fertilizers through traditional methods has led to a series of environmental issues due to the accumulation of heavy elements in the soil[3] This is particularly evident in the case of the Central Kyzylkum phosphate deposit, known for its mineralogical composition and structure, and its processing methods such as (flotation, washing, desliming, thermal processing, and calcium oxide leaching)[6]. However, these low-quality and complex phosphate fertilizers are rarely utilized to improve agricultural productivity. Additionally, the acid processing of the extracted concentrate to produce standard fertilizers results in the generation of large amounts of liquid, solid, and gaseous waste, such as phosphogypsum and fluorine gas emissions. These by-products necessitate additional ecological measures. Despite these challenges, the use of concentrated phosphorus fertilizers in forms such as superphosphate and ammonium phosphate is economically viable. However, their application to soil introduces soluble nutrients, which often leach into water bodies, causing contamination with heavy metals and toxic substances. Phosphorus, due to its low water solubility, tends to accumulate in the upper layers of the soil without being washed away. Of the phosphorus present in the applied fertilizers, 20–25% is absorbed by plants in the first year, while 40–60% is absorbed within 2–3 years. Phosphorus fertilizers increase crop yields and improve quality. For instance, they boost starch content in potatoes and sugar content in sugar beets. A lack of phosphorus leads to wilting and discoloration of plant leaves, with plants growing weakly as a result. As phosphorus is essential for life, it is considered as important as nitrogen and potassium. It is part of cell protoplasm, chromosomes, and enzymes, and is found in the bodies of plants and animals. In cases of phosphorus deficiency, it is advisable to use manure and other organic fertilizers to meet the phosphorus needs of plants. The issue of phosphorus fertilizers has been studied and implemented practically by scientists such as A.N. Engelgardt, V.V. Dokuchaev, P.A. Kostichev, D.N. Pryanishnikov, and J. Cattarov. These fertilizers have since been widely adopted in our country.

Today, agriculture commonly employs the following phosphorus fertilizers:

Phosphorite Powder ($\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$): A natural phosphorus compound or an enriched mixture of phosphorite. Phosphorite powder dissolves poorly in water and is thus recommended for use on saline and acidic soils. Being the cheapest phosphorus mineral fertilizer, it is advised for plants grown on sod and peat soils.

Simple Superphosphate ($\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$): This fertilizer is obtained by treating apatite or phosphorite with sulfuric acid, as shown in the reaction: $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$

→ $\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2 + \text{CaSO}_4$. This phosphorus mineral fertilizer dissolves in water and can be used for plants grown in any soil type.

The elemental composition of phosphorus fertilizers applied to soil is studied using neutron activation methods. Table 1 provides data on the quantities of various chemical elements in soil samples collected from three districts in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. We compare the quantities of specific elements in the soils of the agricultural lands of the region under study.

Thorium and Uranium. The highest concentration of thorium was found in the soil of Nukus district (6.3 mg/kg), followed by Ellikqala district (5.2 mg/kg), while the lowest concentration was detected in the soil of Muynak district (4.88 mg/kg)(Table 1). In the case of uranium, the opposite trend is observed: Ellikqala district (2.82 mg/kg), Muynak district (2.60 mg/kg), and Nukus district (2.10 mg/kg).

These elements, while naturally occurring, are also commonly found in the composition of processed mineral fertilizers, including phosphorus fertilizers.

It is necessary to conclude that the data obtained show that in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, in arable lands, the average indicators are approximately 1.05 and 1.2 times higher [1]. It was determined that the concentration of these elements in the soil has not significantly increased.

Antimony. The highest concentration of antimony was found in the soil of the Ellikqala district (3.60 mg/kg), while the lowest concentration was recorded in Nukus (2.25 mg/kg). This element enters the soil primarily through the composition of pesticides. Our findings on antimony indicate that it does not exert a significant anthropogenic impact on the surrounding environment. However, additional studies are required to understand the involvement of this antimony in the biogeochemical cycle. When comparing our results to the data provided in [1.2.5-7], it can be observed that over 8–10 years (as our samples were taken from the same points), the top layer of soil has become enriched with Na, Sc, Mn, Fe, Co, Rb, Sb, Cs, Ba, La, Ce, Eu, Tb, Th, U, and other microelements [1].

Table 1. The concentration of chemical elements in the topsoil of districts in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (mg/kg).

	Ellikqala	Muynak region		Nukus region		\bar{C}	$\bar{C}[1]$	$\bar{C} / \bar{C}[1]$
	\bar{C}_3	\bar{C}_M	\bar{C}_M / \bar{C}_3	\bar{C}_H	\bar{C}_H / \bar{C}_3			
Na%	1,3	4,5	3,5	2,8	2,2	2,87	1,7	1,69
K%	1,1	1,58	1,43	2,2	2,0	1,63	1,8	0,91
Sc	11,5	7,3	0,60	9,8	0,8	9,54	7,8	1,22
Cr	46,7	25,8	0,50	55,0	1,1	24,3	75,3	0,32
Mn	624,0	450,0	0,72	496,8	0,80	523,6	434	1,21
Fe%	1,85	1,52	0,84	1,35	0,73	1,57	1,4	1,12
Co	11,7	8,2	0,70	9,84	0,86	9,91	8,9	1,11
Rb	35,9	50,9	1,42	41,2	1,15	56	52,7	1,06
Y	29,0	34,0	1,17	33,0	1,3	32	-	-
Zr	11,0	13,2	1,2	12,4	1,1	12,2	-	-

Sb	3,6	2,61	0,72	2,25	0,61	2,82	1,6	1,76
Cs	6,50	3,86	0,59	3,50	0,54	4,29	1,6	2,68
Ba	967,0	635,0	0,66	400,0	0,41	667,3	340	1,96
La	33,6	19,2	0,57	26,9	0,80	26,53	19	1,59
Ce	30,6	26,7	0,87	27,0	0,73	28,1	18,1	1,56
Sm	2,5	2,1	0,84	3,7	1,48	2,77	2,9	0,96
Eu	0,90	1,07	1,18	1,72	1,91	1,23	1,0	1,23
Tb	3,7	3,5	0,95	5,2	1,41	4,13	3,3	1,25
Yb	1,2	1,50	1,25	1,38	1,15	1,36	1,8	0,78
Hf	2,3	2,12	0,91	2,30	1,0	2,21	3,5	0,63
Th	5,2	4,88	0,94	6,3	1,21	5,7	5,3	1,1
U	2,82	2,60	0,93	2,1	0,75	2,51	2,1	1,2

In recent years, cotton stalks have been grown in the soil sampling locations (except in Muynak) to study chemical elements in agricultural lands. As a result, the decrease in the concentrations of K, Cr, Sm, Yb, and Hf in the soil may be related to their high demand by cotton plants. The enrichment process of the soil with elements such as Na, Sb, Cs, Ba, La, and Ce is attributed to activities like salt washing, plowing, the introduction of aerosol particles, the application of mineral fertilizers (e.g., RZE, Sc, Th, U), and the rise of groundwater containing high concentrations of many chemical elements.

Based on data from the Land Cadastre Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the concentration of chemical elements in the topsoil layer has increased by 1.05 to 2.6 times over the past 10 years. To confirm the accuracy of these findings, systematic studies need to be conducted.

Currently, Karatau phosphate is primarily used as a phosphorus fertilizer in the Republic of Uzbekistan. When studying its elemental composition, it was found that heavy natural radioactive elements such as thorium (Th) and uranium (U) may accumulate significantly in the soil. According

to our measurements, the concentration of Th is (0.57mk/kg) and U is (14,2mk/kg), with their uptake by plants being very low, as they are classified as heavy metals. In contrast, the concentrations in Karelian phosphate are Th (15.2 mkg/kg) and U (84 mkg/kg), while in Shyrshyk phosphate, Th was not detected, and U was found at 90mk/kg. Furthermore, significant amounts of other heavy elements in phosphate fertilizers are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Presence of Heavy Elements in Phosphate Fertilizers

Element	Phosphate Fertilizers		
	Karatau	Karelia.	Shyrshyk
Na%	0,38	0,96	0,087
K%	0,70	-	4,0
Sc	0,91	16,5	1,62
Cr	23,4	-	58
Mn	2342	-	310
Fe%	0,40	3	1,0
Co	4,02	20	9,4
Cu	-	-	14
Zn	17,6	165	40
As	18,4	13	30
Se	-	9,1	6,3
Rb	9,8	31	-
Sr	506	1000	80
Sb	1,38	5	0,6
Cs	4,4	8	-
Ba	145	-	-
Lu	17,9	196	210;
Ce	27,9	360	300
Sm	0,67	-	3,1
Eu	0,64	8,0(28)	1,3
Tb	0,25	1,7	1,0
Yb	2,0	22,5	-
Lu	0.14	3.2	-
Hf	0.31	-	-
Ta	-	0,2	-
Au	0,008	0,003	0,005
Th	0,57	15,2	-
U	14,2	84	90
Br	-	25.5	-
Ni	-	2,8	-
Ca	-	-	6,0
Hg	-	-	0,10
Cd	-	-	70

Conclusion

In summary, it should be noted that the concentrations of many elements in the soil are very low (except for Na and K). The dusty reactions of the surrounding environment and the oxidation state of elements in the Aral Sea region result in their low mobility. As a consequence, plants, animals, and humans may suffer from deficiencies of these elements, which is reflected in the declining fertility of the region's soil. Soil salinization has disrupted the regular migration patterns of chemical elements in the region's biosphere. Due to this, the accumulation of bioactive elements has decreased, and the concentration coefficients among elements have been disrupted. Therefore, it is essential to study the broad-spectrum distribution patterns of chemical elements along the soil profile. If phosphorus fertilizers are continuously applied to specific areas over many years, the natural composition of radioactive elements in the soil significantly increases. As a result, harmful elements accumulate in those areas, leading to adverse ecological conditions. The deterioration in the quality of obtained products affects living organisms, leading to the emergence of various diseases.

REFERENCES

1. Jumamratov A. et al. Сравнительный элементный состав современных и скрытых почв Приаралья. // *Geochemistry. RAS.* – Moscow: 2001. № 3. – pp. 342–348.
2. Jumamuratov A. Загрязнение почв тяжелыми элементами при антропогенном воздействии Южного Приаралья. // *Journal of Natural and Technical Sciences.* – Moscow, 2004. № 2. – pp. 146–147.
3. Минеральные удобрения. Translated from German by N.S. Korogodov and G.P. Shultsev. – Moscow: Koles, 1975. – 458 p.
4. Свидетельство на стандартный образец SP-1. Research Institute of Industrial Chemistry, Irkutsk State University. – Irkutsk, 1975.
5. Jumamuratov A. Изучение элементного сдвига состава почв методом математического моделирования при севооборотах. *Bulletin of KKO of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.* – Nukus, 2005. № 1–2. – pp. 54–57.
6. Jumamuratov A. et al. Исследование содержания элементов в фосфоритном сырье Султануездага. // *Bulletin of KKO of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.* – Nukus, 1997. № 5. – pp. 24–26.
7. Jumamuratov A., Khatamov Sh., Tillayev T. Распределение химических элементов по земельному профилю Каракалпакии. // *Journal of Agriculture.* – Moscow, 2003. – p. 13.